

The Reformed Church (Early Orthodoxy)

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Reformed/Presbyterian/Congregational/United, Protestantism, Abrahamic

The period often identified as Reformed orthodoxy (alternatively, Reformed scholasticism) within the history of the Reformed church lasts from approximately 1560 until 1800. It is traditionally subdivided into three shorter periods: early orthodoxy (1560–1620), high orthodoxy (1620–1700), and late orthodoxy (1700–1800). Most historians fix the beginning of early orthodoxy to the transition from the second to the third generation of reformers, as Peter Martyr Vermigli (d. 1562), Wolfgang Musculus (d. 1563), John Calvin (d. 1564), and their second-generation peers were replaced by Theodore Beza, Zacharius Ursinus, Girolamo Zanchi, and others. It was a period of solidification for the Reformed tradition, witnessing the spread of confessional statements of faith—including the Gallic Confession (1559), Belgic Confession (1561), Second Helvetic Confession (1562), Heidelberg Catechism (1563), and eventually the Canons of Dort (1619)—which delineated the boundaries of the Reformed faith and reinforced its differences with other forms of Protestantism. The theology of the period is marked by a return to the scholastic method of the late medieval period and the rise of intra-Reformed disputes about particular theological doctrines (e.g., predestination), a trend which intensified throughout the first half of the seventeenth century as disputes turned increasingly to the minutiae of Reformed theology. The end of early orthodoxy has been located as early as 1620 (with the Canons of Dort serving as the approximate conclusion of the period in Willem van Asselt's periodization) to as late as the 1640s (with the end of the Thirty Years' War and the Westminster Assembly marking the transition in Richard Muller's periodization).

Date Range: 1560 CE - 1620 CE

Region: Reformed Church in Early Modern Europe

Region tags: Europe, Northern Britain, Scotland, Germany, England, Eastern Europe

Reformed Protestantism spread throughout western and eastern Europe during this period, including throughout England, Scotland, France, Switzerland, the Netherlands, the Holy Roman Empire, Poland-Lithuania, and Hungary.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Herman Selderhuis, ed., *A Companion to Reformed Orthodoxy* (Leiden: Brill, 2013)
- Source 2: Richard Muller, *Post-Reformation Reformed Dogmatics: The Rise and Development of Reformed Orthodoxy, ca. 1520 to 1725*, vol. 1-4, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2003)
- Source 3: Philip Benedict, *Christ's Churches Purely Reformed: A Social History of Calvinism* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2002)

- Source 1: Willem van Asselt, *Introduction to Reformed Scholasticism* (Grand Rapids, MI: Reformation Heritage Books, 2011)
- Source 2: D. G. Hart, *Calvinism: A History* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2013)
- Source 3: Richard Muller, *After Calvin: Studies in the Development of a Theological Tradition* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://plato.stanford.edu/index.html>
- Source 1 Description: Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy, which includes entries for many earlier theologians and philosophers whose ideas shaped early modern Reformed theology

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.prdl.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Post-Reformation Digital Library, a collection of digital texts on theology and philosophy during the early modern period

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Catholic, Lutheran, Reformed, and Anabaptist Christians were in regular contact across the European continent. Regions often fluctuated from one confessional tradition to another as wars were fought, alliances were formed, and rulers were replaced. Cross-confessional contact existed not only between different regions but also within the population of each particular region, as individual cities, villages, and families often found themselves standing in opposition to the official religion in their land.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Conflict between different Christian traditions during this period was highly competitive, as each viewed its position as the sole true expression of the Christian faith.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: Although religious toleration was certainly not the default, there were periods of relatively peaceful coexistence between competing religious traditions across the continent. See Benjamin Kaplin, *Divided by Faith: Religious Conflict and the Practice of Toleration in Early Modern Europe* (Cambridge: Belknap Press, 2007). Wayne Te Brake, *Religious War and Religious Peace in Early Modern Europe* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Conflict between different religious traditions ranged from extended wars between competing empires to the persecution of heretical individuals or minority religious groups. Notable wars involving Reformed Christians during this period included the French Wars of Religion and the Eighty Years' War. See Anton van der Lem, *Revolt in the Netherlands: The Eighty Years' War*, trans. Andy Brown (London: Reaktion Books, 2018). Philip Benedict, ed., *Reformation, Revolt and Civil War in France and the Netherlands* (Amsterdam: Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences, 1999). Mack Holt, *The French Wars of Religion, 1562-1629* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995). Brad Gregory, *Salvation at Stake: Christian Martyrdom in Early Modern Europe* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1999). Nicholas Terpstra, *Religious Refugees in the Early Modern World: An Alternative History of the Reformation* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to conflict with other Christian traditions in western and central Europe, the ever-present external threat of the Ottoman Empire loomed in eastern Europe.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Although the Reformed rejected certain aspects of the Catholic doctrine of baptism (notably baptismal regeneration), they did not reject paedobaptism altogether (as the Anabaptists did). The Reformed doctrine of baptism developed as part of a broader system of covenant theology, whereby baptism marked children as members of the covenant community, or the Christian church.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Whether baptized as a child or not, all adults were expected to consciously commit to the faith.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed tradition recognized two sacraments: baptism (see above) and the Lord's Supper (alternatively, the eucharist), both of which served to mark members of their Christian community. For distinctive aspects of the eucharist in each tradition, see Lee Palmer Wandel, *The Eucharist in the Reformation* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2006).

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: This mandate had long been recognized in the Christian church, based upon (among other passages) commands in Mark 16 and Matthew 28. The Reformed maintained this longstanding Christian commitment to proselytization, although during this period, their evangelistic efforts did not extend far beyond the borders of Europe.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– Yes

Notes: The frequent threat of physical violence to religious minorities served as an obvious impetus for conversion.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– Yes

Notes: Those who refused to yield to the religion of the land (whether Catholics in Reformed lands or Reformed in Catholics lands) were subject not only to physical danger but also social and economic marginalization.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The religion of any given land in early modern Europe was determined by its ruler, and no minority religion could hope to survive or spread without the support of at least a portion of the elite class. The support of certain French nobility, for instance, was critical to the survival of the Reformed faith in France throughout the French Wars of Religion. See Mack Holt, *The French Wars of Religion, 1562-1629* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995).

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: Although the church often funded its own infrastructure and operations, there were certainly times when the state contributed its finances as well.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: Although this was generally not the case, there were exceptions, as in England after the 1534 Act of Supremacy which declared Henry VIII (rather than the pope) the Head of the Church of England. See Peter Marshall, *Heretics and Believers: A History of the English Reformation* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2017).

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Notes: Although this was not common in the Reformed church as it was amongst Catholic bishops, the nobility and local magistrate did have significant influence within the church. The extent of this influence and the formal roles they held varied from one place to the next.

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Accusations of apostasy (and more generally heresy) were frequently leveled against members of competing religious traditions (e.g., Lutherans or Catholics).

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are physically marked as such (e.g. branding, mutilation):

– No

↳ Apostates are executed:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are publicly executed:

– Yes

↳ Other corporal punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Torture and other forms of corporal punishment

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates (and more generally unbelievers and heretics of any sort) would be cast into hell.

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Yes

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Various temporal punishments

Notes: Although temporal punishment was not guaranteed, the temporal afflictions and sufferings of apostates, heretics, and others in competing religious traditions were frequently described as a form of divine punishment. See Alexandra Walsham, *Providence in Early Modern England* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2001).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Philip Benedict placed the number of Christians worshipping in Reformed churches in Europe at approximately 10 million in 1600, but it is simply not possible to provide an accurate estimate. First and foremost, whatever the number was, it would have changed constantly and rapidly, as entire kingdoms converted en masse with the ascension of a new ruler, throwing the numbers wildly in one direction or another. It is also frequently unclear who counts as Reformed (e.g., the Anglican church appears more Reformed at certain points and far less Reformed at others). For Benedict's estimate, see Philip Benedict, *Christ's Churches Purely Reformed: A Social History of Calvinism* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2002), 281-82.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: It is not possible to estimate this accurately. See above comments on number of adherents.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (intolerant of other affiliations)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Reformed church rejected the hierarchy of the Roman Church, they adopted various hierarchical church polities of their own, ranging from episcopalianism in the Church of England to presbyterianism in the Church of Scotland.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: Although they were a minority, certain congregationalist churches within the broader Reformed tradition adopted an independent polity wherein each church was led by an individual who was both selected by and accountable to the members of that individual church rather than a broader hierarchical church government.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Episcopalian churches, such as the Church of England, were overseen by a single leader.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Presbyterian churches, such as the Church of Scotland, were overseen by a group of leaders.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

Notes: This is not possible to estimate as it varied widely from one church polity to the next.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
– Yes

Notes: Selection process for religious leaders varied based upon the particular polity (e.g., presbyterian, episcopalian, congregationalist) described above.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
– Yes

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
– Yes

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
– Yes

Notes: Contra Rome, the Reformed Church did not invest its leaders with any measure of infallibility, regardless of the particular polity under consideration.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed church rejected the canonical status of the apocryphal books but continued to use the remainder of the Old and New Testaments as their holy scriptures.

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed tradition insisted upon the divine inspiration and infallibility of the scriptures.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: Christian churches, many quite massive, existed across the continent, but they cover a small fraction of the total land area of Europe.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

- ↳ Tombs:
 - Yes

- ↳ Cemeteries:
 - Yes

- ↳ Temples:
 - Yes

- ↳ Altars:
 - No

Notes: The removal of the altar marked one of the key differences between a Catholic and Reformed church in the late sixteenth century.

- ↳ Devotional markers:
 - Yes

- ↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
 - No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

- ↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
 - On persons
 - At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: One of the distinctives of the Reformed tradition was its rejection of icons and images. This set the Reformed apart not only from the Catholics but also from the Lutherans, who were far less militant than the Reformed on this point. Icons and images of all kinds frequently fell victim to iconoclastic destruction at the hands of Reformed Christians, and Reformed churches were soon bare and unadorned across the continent. See Margaret Aston, *England's Iconoclasts* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1988). Carlos Eire, *War Against the Idols* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1989). Lee Palmer Wandel, *Voracious Idols and Violent Hands: Iconoclasm in Reformation Zurich, Strasbourg, and Basel* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1995).

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Reformed theologians rejected the notion of sacred sites, and older historiography often spoke of the Reformation as a form of disenchantment. More recent work, however, has shown that various forms of enchantment, including sacred sites and landscapes, persisted at the popular level despite official denunciations. See Alexandra Walsham, *The Reformation of the Landscape: Religion, Identity, and Memory in Early Modern Britain and Ireland* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2011). Euan Cameron, *Enchanted Europe: Superstition, Religion, and Reason 1250-1700* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010). Robert Scribner, "The Reformation, Popular Magic, and the 'Disenchantment of the World'," *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History* 23, no. 3 (1993): 475-94.

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Once more, Reformed leaders sought to disabuse their congregations of such notions, but many environmental features retained their sacred aura at the popular level.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: The rejection of sacred sites and objects implied a corresponding rejection of pilgrimage to such sites. Calvin famously requested an unmarked grave to prevent it from becoming a pilgrimage site. However, such practices frequently persisted at a popular level.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Reformed scholastics, following long-standing Christian tradition, believed in a distinction between body and soul. However, the broader anthropology they produced differed in many ways from earlier Catholic doctrine. While Catholic thinkers often emphasized the finitude (and thus imperfection) of nature, the Reformed insisted upon the ontological perfection of nature (and humanity) in the prelapsarian world. This entailed a different view of the relationship between nature and grace, with the Reformed defining grace as a corrective for sin rather than a corrective for nature qua nature. This more optimistic prelapsarian anthropology was counterbalanced, in some sense, by a more pessimistic postlapsarian anthropology, as the Reformed emphasized the severe effects of the fall and the subsequent moral depravity of humanity. Nevertheless, they looked forward to the

restoration of fallen nature at the second coming of Christ.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed rejected the Catholic doctrine of purgatory but maintained otherwise traditional views about heaven and hell. The soteriological emphasis on substitutionary atonement produced a particular vision of hell where divine wrath served as the source of punishment and suffering, but generally, Reformed scholastics avoided novelty in their discussions of heaven and hell.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Although cosmological convictions were very much in flux during this period, many Aristotelians (including Reformed, Lutheran, and Catholics) located heaven somewhere beyond the outermost sphere of the fixed stars.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical language frequently alludes to heaven as something “above” and hell as something “below.”

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Notes: Biblical language frequently alludes to heaven as something “above” and hell as something “below.”

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed doctrine of God differed from both Catholic and Lutheran doctrines in many ways. They all believed, of course, in a Trinitarian God, and dissent on this point was not tolerated in any confessional tradition. However, the minutiae of their doctrine of God--to include his attributes (e.g., omniscience, immutability, will), his method of operation and oversight within the world (e.g., providence), and even the details of the Trinity itself (e.g., the relationship of each person to the others)--varied substantially, not only between the Reformed, Lutherans, and Catholics, but also within the Reformed tradition itself.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: In the person of Christ, the Christian God was not merely anthropomorphic, he was quite literally human. The Bible also frequently uses anthropomorphic and anthropopathic language to describe God the Father, but the Reformed insisted that this language was not meant to be taken literally. They typically explained it either as a figure of speech or a form of accommodated communication.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Divine Ordination of Rulers

Notes: The Reformed generally upheld the traditional view that rulers were ordained by God, but how they reconciled this conviction with their justifications for rebellion against ungodly (e.g., Catholic) rulers varied from one theologian to the next.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
– Yes

Notes: The Reformed insisted upon the omniscience of God. This knowledge of God was all-encompassing. God knew all things always, and he knew them all perfectly. Although this was far from a novel position and many within the Catholic church held similar convictions, this period did witness the rise of alternative perspectives that limited the knowledge of God to one extent or another, with Socinianism appearing within the Reformed tradition and Molinism within the Catholic church.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed insisted upon the omnipotence of God and his providential control of all things. Similar to their views on divine knowledge, Reformed ideas about divine power and providence were far from novel. However, this period did witness the rise of alternative perspectives, laying the groundwork for the detailed disputes about divine power, will, and intellect that would play out during the seventeenth century.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Although the Reformed insisted that God providentially controlled all things, they also believed that he could (and often did) work through intermediaries (e.g., angels) and secondary causes (e.g., nature)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– No

Notes: The Reformed typically insisted upon the impassibility of God. They explained biblical references to positive divine emotions (e.g., joy) as figures of speech or

accommodated communication.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

Notes: The Reformed typically insisted upon the impassibility of God. They explained biblical references to negative divine emotions (e.g., regret, sadness) as figures of speech or accommodated communication.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: The Bible and the preached Word of God

Notes: The Reformed placed a significant emphasis upon the Bible and the preached Word of God (i.e., the sermon) as God's primary methods of communication with humanity. Most did not deny the possibility of communication via other means, but they understood such cases as exceptions rather than the norm.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: Although there were, of course, certain exceptions to this rule, such as the appearance of Moses and Elijah at the transfiguration of Christ.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Both angels and demons (i.e., fallen angels) are present and active on the earth.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Although they are typically not visible, there are many biblical examples of angels appearing visibly to humans. Reformed scholastics viewed such events as exceptional occurrences which took place during unique periods in history. They generally shunned the type of divine visions or supernatural encounters with saints promoted by the Catholic Church at the time.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Given the Reformed commitment to the sovereignty and omnipotence of God, angels and demons could operate within this world, but only within the parameters allowed by God.

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: Orthodox Christian traditions, including the Reformed, viewed Jesus as both human and divine. The Reformed maintained the traditional, orthodox view of the hypostatic union, insisting upon two natures (divine and human) within the one person of Christ, and condemning heresies that attempted to divorce the person of Christ into two (e.g., Nestorianism) or conflate the natures of Christ into one (e.g., monophysitism).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

Notes: In accordance with long-standing Christian views, the Reformed believed that divine prohibitions on certain foods had passed away with the old covenant.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Although the doctrine of imago dei (as well as the prohibitions on murder in Genesis 9, Exodus 20, Deuteronomy 5, and elsewhere) suggested that any murder, regardless of the victim, was wrong, there was certainly more empathy for the death of fellow Protestants than for Catholics or unbelievers (e.g., Muslims in the east).

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, the murder of members of other religions was unacceptable according to most theologians. Nevertheless, popular fervor sometimes trumped such theoretical objections, and the murder of "heretics" and "unbelievers" was not only tolerated but encouraged, a cleansing of the sinful from the community. While the largest and most famous riots and popular violence were carried out by Catholics against the Protestants (e.g., the St. Bartholomew's Day massacre), the Reformed certainly engaged in similar violence at times.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Although sexual sin (premarital sex, adultery, etc.) was, of course, forbidden, there is significant evidence that it was relatively widespread during this period, and punishments were sometimes minimal or nonexistent.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premarital sex

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed emphasis on the value of work has become a historical commonplace, with Max Weber famously crediting this Protestant (and specifically Calvinist) work ethic with creating capitalism, Robert Merton crediting it with the growth of science, and countless others defending or refuting similar claims. Whether such claims have any legitimacy or not, it is true that the Reformed emphasized the value of work (and attacked laziness, sluggishness,

and idleness) more than other Christian traditions.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed believed God sovereignly and providentially governed all things. Thus in some sense, every punishment, whether it came directly by divine intervention in the world or indirectly through some secondary cause (angels, demons, other humans, or even natural causes) ultimately came from God. There is another sense, though, in which these punishments came through secondary causes, such as the angel of death slaying the firstborn sons of Egypt (at the command of God) or Satan tormenting Job (with the permission of God).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: See the previous comment on God's use of supernatural beings as secondary agents of divine punishment.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the great and final punishment of hell, sin and wickedness did sometimes (but not always) elicit temporal punishment, and this sometimes (but not always) came by way of secondary causes (e.g., nature), directed by the providence of God.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Sin was the reason for all punishment, both temporal and eternal.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The final punishment was, of course, hell, where unbelievers would suffer for eternity under the just wrath of God for their sins.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the great and final punishment of hell, sin and wickedness did sometimes (but not always) elicit temporal punishment. Reformed preachers frequently exhorted suffering parishioners to repent of their sins in the hope that God might relent.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: At an individual level, the far greater concern was the eternal, spiritual punishment of hell. But at a collective level, the success or failure of churches, nations, and empires was viewed (not only by the Reformed but by nearly everyone) as indicative of God's favor or displeasure. Thus each side heralded their fortunes (e.g., victory in war) as a sign of God's support for their cause.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: See note above.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: See note above.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Faith was the cause of the final and great spiritual reward of heaven, while righteousness was often viewed as the cause of temporal rewards in this life. However, just as wickedness did not guarantee divine punishment in this life, righteousness did not guarantee divine favor in this life. There was a certain unpredictability to God's actions while humans remained on this earth, and the Reformed made ample use of Job to demonstrate that Christians must bear their lot gladly, as no one should question God.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed believed God sovereignly and providentially governed all things. Thus in some sense, every reward (like every punishment), whether it came directly by divine intervention in the world or indirectly through some secondary cause (angels, other humans, or even natural causes) ultimately came from God. There is another sense, though, in which these rewards came through secondary causes, such as Gabriel visiting Mary to tell her that she would give birth to the Messiah.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: See the previous comment on God's use of supernatural beings as secondary agents of divine rewards.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
– Yes

↳ Done randomly:
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– No

↳ Other [specify]
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Although the Bible explicitly states that the time of Christ's return cannot be known, the extensive religious conflict of the period led many--Reformed, Lutheran, and Catholic alike--to speculate that his return was close.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Although there was broad agreement about the purpose of Christ's return--the defeat Satan, the redemption of God's people, and the restoration of the world--there was not universal agreement about the precise details and timeline, and multiple eschatological perspectives coexisted within the Reformed tradition throughout the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Notes: The Reformed explicitly rejected this idea as an error of the Jews.

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Defeat of Satan, redemption of God's people, and restoration of the world

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: There was disagreement over various eschatological details within the Reformed tradition during this period.

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Notes: Whether the eschaton was distant or near was unknown, although many suspected that the turmoil of their day may presage the end.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: Whether the eschaton was distant or near was unknown, although many suspected that the turmoil of their day may presage the end.

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: Although all humans will survive the eschaton (and all the dead will be raised), the Reformed, like most Christian traditions, insisted that Christians would be raised to eternal life while unbelievers would be condemned to hell.

↳ Other survival condition:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society
– All individuals within contemporary world
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– No

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Yes
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The rejection of clerical celibacy distinguished Protestant clergy from their Catholic counterparts.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the enforcement of monogamous marriage, premarital sex was forbidden.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the enforcement of monogamous marriage, pre-martial sex was forbidden.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Although there were no set requirements concerning how often or how long one must fast, fasting remained a prominent aspect of religious life in the Reformed tradition.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

Notes: Charity was typically directed to other members of the same religious community, rather than to members of any competing religious tradition.

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Although Reformed ideas about the Sabbath took different shades in different areas (and continued to develop throughout the seventeenth century), all Reformed traditions marked Sunday as their holy day. They demanded church attendance on the Sabbath (though this does not mean everyone listened) and encouraged regular private prayer and Bible reading.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: The Reformed tradition rejected much of the ritual life of Catholicism, viewing everything from the sign of the cross to wedding rings as unbiblical superstition. How far they succeeded in eliminating such rituals from the daily life of the common people remains a point of contention, but on an official level, these things were condemned. They did maintain their own rituals of course (e.g., the sacraments of baptism and the Lord's Supper), but most of the small-scale ritualistic practices that took place in private were condemned. For the resilience of such rituals even under Protestant rule, see Eamon Duffy, *The Stripping of the Altars: Traditional Religion in England, 1400-1580* (New Haven: Yale, 2002) and Eamon Duffy, *The Voices of Morebath: Reformation and Rebellion in an English Village* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2001).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: See earlier comments on baptism and the Lord's Supper.

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The number of participants in such activities could vary wildly, from a small parish church to a massive urban gathering.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: Baptism occurred only once in a person's life, and the frequency of the Lord's Supper varied from weekly in some churches to annually in others.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The development of confessions and catechisms during this period helped solidify the doctrinal boundaries of the tradition.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Notes: The Reformed maintained that circumcision had been replaced by the sacrament of baptism.

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– No

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Ancient Christian creeds and confessions, such as the Apostles' Creed, maintained a prominent place in the Reformed tradition.

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: Baptism

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: Like most Christian traditions, the Reformed frequently uses familial language--chiefly "brothers and sisters"--to refer to other Christians, language modeled for them by the Bible.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Poverty and famine relief were critical missions within all traditions of early modern Christianity.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Poverty and famine relief were critical missions within all traditions of early modern Christianity.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Reformed, like the Lutherans, placed an enormous emphasis upon childhood education, convinced that their best chance to convert the population lay in the proper education of the youth. This included both early childhood education (see Johann Sturm's gymnasium in Strasbourg) and advanced university education (see the academy, and eventually university, in Geneva). See Karin Maag, *Seminary or University? The Genevan Academy and Reformed Higher Education, 1560–1620* (Aldershot: Scholar Press, 1995).

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Although education was available, at certain times and in certain places, to both boys and girls, opportunities for young girls were far more limited.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Although education was available, at certain times and in certain places, to both boys and girls, opportunities for young girls were far more limited.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Although structures of authority varied widely from one Reformed location to the next, regardless of polity, Reformed churches placed some measure authority in the hands of ministers and other church leaders. Formal civil judges were provided by the civil authorities, but the church authorities wrestled for influence as well. How far this authority stretched and where the boundary between church and civil authority lay was a frequent point of contention, but the leaders of the church typically maintained some influence over matters that could be construed as moral or religious in any way.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Even in cases where the church wielded the authority to judge some contested matter--such as heresy--it was typically the state that subsequently enforced the punishment. Although this, like all other aspects of church and civil governance, varied widely from one part of Europe to the next.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No